

Progression of Physical Constants Derived from Planck Units

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2025

Constant	Formula	Value (SI units)	Planck Unit Equivalent
Planck Length	$l_P = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^3}}$	1.616×10^{-35} m	$1 l_P$
Planck Time	$t_P = \frac{l_P}{c}$	5.391×10^{-44} s	$1 t_P$
Planck Mass	$m_P = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c}{G}}$	2.176×10^{-8} kg	$1 m_P$
Planck Charge	$q_P = \sqrt{4\pi\epsilon_0 \hbar c}$	1.875×10^{-18} C	$1 q_P$
Planck Energy	$E_P = m_P c^2$	1.956×10^9 J	$1 E_P$
Planck Temperature	$T_P = \frac{m_P c^2}{k_B}$	1.416×10^{32} K	$1 T_P$
Gravitational Constant	$G = \frac{l_P^2}{m_P t_P^2}$	6.674×10^{-11} m ³ /kg · s ²	$\frac{l_P^2}{m_P t_P^2}$
Fine-Structure Constant	$\alpha = \frac{q_P^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 \hbar c}$	1/137.03599	$\frac{q_P^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 \hbar c}$
Maxwell's Equation	$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0}$	\mathbf{E} in N/C, $\epsilon_0 = 8.854 \times 10^{-12}$ F/m	$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0}$ (in Planck units)
Schwarzschild Radius	$r_s = \frac{2GM}{c^2}$	r_s in meters	$r_s = \frac{2Gm_P}{c^2}$ (Planck equivalent)
Einstein's Equation	$E = mc^2$	E in joules	$E_P = m_P c^2$ (Planck equivalent)

Table 1: Derivation of Fundamental Constants from Planck Units